

Didactic Conditions of Social-Pedagogical Competence Development in Leaders of Educational Institutions

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Abstract:

This article describes the didactic conditions for the development of competence, competence, pedagogical competence, socio-pedagogical competence, social-pedagogical competence in the heads of educational institutions.

Keywords: Competence, competence, pedagogical competence, social-pedagogical competence, didactic conditions for the development of social-pedagogical competence in the heads of educational institutions.

The main condition for the development of pedagogical competence is the teacher's understanding of the need for improvement. Universal and special culture, as well as the ability to organize pedagogical communication. The ideas of integrity, unity, systematic organization of the teacher's work allow to present the teacher's work - a complex pedagogical reality - in the form of a unity of three interrelated spaces. Teacher's personality, pedagogical activity and pedagogical activity. At the same time, the integral characteristics of the teacher's personality - pedagogical direction, pedagogical competence, emotional flexibility - determine the effectiveness of the teacher's activity and are the object of the teacher's professional development (self-development). The main condition for the teacher's professional and pedagogical development is the transition to a higher level of pedagogical consciousness. The personal internal conflicts of the teacher, the opposing unity of the reflective "I" of the teacher are the driving force for the development of pedagogical competence [1].

In the context of studying the phenomenon of pedagogical competence, first of all, it is necessary to consider the history of the formation of the concepts of "competence", "competence", "pedagogical competence", which reveals not only the dynamics. understands the content of concepts, but also their content at the current stage of science development.

Aristotle can be called the founder of the competence approach, he studied the possibilities of the human condition defined by the Greek word "atere" - a power developed and perfected to such an extent that it became a characteristic of the individual. However, according to some researchers, the use of the concepts of "competence" and "competence" began in the United States in 1958 and is marked by significant achievements.

At the end of the twentieth century, a stable opinion about the meaning of the concepts of "competence" and "competence" was formed in the European scientific tradition. In the glossary of the European Education Foundation, the concept of "competence" is defined as follows:

1. The ability to do any job well or efficiently.
2. Compliance with labor requirements.
3. The ability to perform certain labor functions.

The concept of "competence" is considered as a characteristic given to a person as a result of evaluating the effectiveness (effectiveness) of his actions aimed at solving a certain number of important tasks (problems) for society. We consider important the conclusion of European researchers that the qualification of a specialist is determined primarily by the results of his professional activity. In this regard, it should be noted that the success of any activity, including teaching, is determined not by what goal is announced within this activity, but by what result is achieved.

The European project "Identification and selection of key competences" is of particular interest in our research, which focuses on the system of competencies required in any activity, including professional and pedagogical activities, which are the key to life success and development. effective functioning of the whole society.

The Council of Europe has identified five core competencies that Europeans should "arm up":

- political and social competencies, such as taking responsibility, participating in collective decision-making, non-violent conflict resolution, participation in maintaining and improving democratic institutions;
- competencies related to life in a multicultural society. In order to control the growth of racism and xenophobia, to control the development of an atmosphere of intolerance, education should provide young people with intercultural competences such as acceptance of differences, respect for others and the ability to live with people of other cultures, languages and religions. ;
- Competencies were related to oral and written communication. They are especially important for work and social life, because people who do not have them are at risk of social exclusion. Knowing several languages in the same communication environment is becoming more and more important;
- competencies related to the growth of the information society. Knowledge of information technologies, their application, understanding of their strengths and weaknesses. Ability to make critical conclusions about the information disseminated by mass media;
- life-long learning as a basis for lifelong learning in the context of personal professional and social life.

The system of basic competencies proposed by European researchers is of practical importance for the development of the system of basic professional and pedagogical competencies because they are universal [2].

In Russian, the meaning of the concept of "competence" has a number of meanings. First of all, it refers to the characteristics of a person that allows to solve and reason in a certain area. Secondly, knowledge, awareness, experience of social and professional activities. In the current national scientific tradition, in the interpretation of the concept of "competence", attention is paid to the importance of the specialist's personal characteristics and his experience.

This conclusion is interesting for understanding not only the essence of the concept of "competence", but also the concept of "pedagogical competence", because in our opinion, the personal qualities of the teacher are of great importance [3].

P.F. Kapterev's ideas are of great interest for the development of the system of pedagogical competencies of teachers (models of competency approach in professional training). The researcher emphasizes that all the personal qualities of the teacher can be objective (the level of knowledge of the teacher in the subject, the level of knowledge of the methodology of the subject and the depth of his scientific knowledge, having general didactic and methodological knowledge). principles, the ability to penetrate the characteristics of child psychology and comprehensive perception) and subjective (art of teaching, pedagogical talent, creativity). In the context of the development of the system of pedagogical competencies, teachers of vocational schools in general and basic vocational education should pay attention to P.F. Kapterev's conclusions about the importance of personal characteristics of teachers for effective educational activities. Defining a set of personal qualities is an important task for our research [4].

Markova emphasizes the connection between the teacher's pedagogical self-awareness and the high results of educational activities as the most important indicator of the former professional and pedagogical competence of the teacher [5].

TE Isaeva reveals the content of professional and personal competencies necessary for successful pedagogical activity in detail and controversially. The researcher determines that:

1. Adaptable and civilized competencies;
2. Social competencies;
3. Social and organizational competencies;
4. Vocational - a set of knowledge, skills, teaching methods, methods of translation of professional and corporate experience, determined based on the specific characteristics of the taught subject and selected in accordance with the pedagogical system. According to this interpretation, the concept of "competence" is broader than the traditional "knowledge" triad. sticks;
5. Communicative;
6. Value and semantics - providing a person with the ability to maintain "himself" in any situation.

In the context of studying the phenomenon of pedagogical competence, I.A.Zimnyaya focuses on the teacher's personal qualities as an important condition for the success of the teacher's professional activity. It is necessary to agree with I.A.Zimnyaya's conclusion that "the most complete interpretation of competence as a personal quality was presented by the developers of the "Strategy for the Modernization of General Education Content".

Based on the analysis of the formation of the concepts of "competition", "competence", "professional competence", "pedagogical competence", the development of their content, as well as approaches to determining their components and hierarchy. the following conclusions can be drawn

regarding their competencies. It is necessary to distinguish a number of basic competences that characterize the versatility of teacher training in vocational education, his social and professional mobility, and his readiness to successfully realize himself as a professional and teacher in the conditions of basic educational institutions. professional education. We understand intercultural and interdisciplinary knowledge, skills and competencies, personal characteristics necessary for effective pedagogical activity as core competencies. Taking into account the existence of special competencies as well as basic competencies within the professional activity of a vocational education teacher, we consider it appropriate to consider the professional competence of vocational education teachers as a unit of basic and special competencies .

The development of socio-pedagogical competence in the heads of educational institutions is important in ensuring the success of the modern education system. This competence includes skills and knowledge necessary for leaders to effectively communicate with teachers and students, organize the educational process, solve social issues, and effectively manage the pedagogical process. Below are the didactic conditions necessary for the development of socio-pedagogical competence:

1. Continuous training of managers

- Heads of the educational institution must constantly participate in professional development courses for the development of socio-pedagogical competence. These courses provide leaders with knowledge on modern education and management methods, socio-pedagogical approaches, conflict management, and development of communication skills.

2. Creating a strong communicative environment

- It is important for leaders to create an effective communication environment in the development of socio-pedagogical competence. Establishing an open and constructive dialogue with teachers, students and their parents in an educational institution increases the competence of the leader. Also, leaders should create a favorable environment for understanding and responding to the needs of students and teachers.

3. Encourage teamwork and cooperation

- In order to develop socio-pedagogical competence, leaders need to encourage teamwork and cooperation. This requires close collaboration with teachers, other leaders and education professionals, sharing experiences and creating joint projects. These abilities of the leader help to improve the general socio-pedagogical environment of the educational institution.

4. Management focused on inclusive education

- Another important condition for the development of socio-pedagogical competence in the implementation of inclusive education is the development of management skills of leaders in this direction. Inclusive education requires leaders to create educational conditions suitable for students with different needs, to adapt pedagogical approaches.

5. Reflective management practices

- Leaders can develop socio-pedagogical competence by regularly analyzing (reflecting) their activities. This process helps them continuously improve their management skills, identify problems and find appropriate solutions. Reflective practices ensure that leaders take a critical approach to their work and continuously improve it.

6. Development of social and cultural competence

- It is important for the leaders of the educational institution to develop their social and cultural competence while developing socio-pedagogical competence. It develops the ability of leaders

to work effectively in different social and cultural conditions, to understand and respect the different cultural backgrounds of students.

7. Decision-making based on scientific research and experience

- Socio-pedagogical competence of leaders is related to making management decisions based on scientific research and experience. This condition directs leaders to use modern scientific research to implement effective management in the educational institution. It is also important to make scientifically based decisions when introducing innovative pedagogical methods in an educational institution.

8. Open and fair leadership

- Another important condition for the development of socio-pedagogical competence in the heads of the educational institution is open and fair leadership. The leader's fairness, objectivity and openness play an important role in their relationship with teachers and students. These aspects strengthen the socio-pedagogical abilities of the leader and improve the general environment of the educational institution.

In conclusion, it can be said that the didactic conditions for the development of socio-pedagogical competence in the leaders of educational institutions serve the leader's effective management of social and pedagogical processes inside and outside the educational institution. These conditions play an important role in improving the quality of education of leaders, contributing to the social development of students, and ensuring the overall effectiveness of the pedagogical process.

List of used literature:

1. Abuzjarova MI 2018; Ashmarov I.A. 2018
2. Aminova D.K., Tsaxaeva, A.A 2018; Borisov VI 2018 yil; Gadzaov AF, Dzerjinskaya MR 2018
3. Gadjieva. UB 2018; Kuznetsov AA, Ignatyeva TA, Kuznetsov AO 2018
4. SAMUSEVIYĀ, A., & STRIGUNA, S. (2017)
5. Voloshina, T. V. (2018).